

RELATIONS BETWEEN CHEMICAL ACTIVITY AND ABSORPTION IN THE
ULTRAVIOLET OF CERTAIN ORGANIC MOLECULES. PART X.
VELOCITY OF HYDROLYSIS OF SUBSTITUTED
AMIDES OF ACETOACETIC ACID

BY R. K. TRIVEDI AND B. N. MANKAD

The substituted amides of acetoacetic acid have been hydrolysed with a standard solution of (i) alcoholic potassium hydroxide, (ii) aqueous hydrochloric acid in order to study the rate of hydrolysis in alkaline and acid media.

The following observations have been made in this connection: (i) Velocity of hydrolysis (especially alkaline) agrees with their absorption spectra, and appears to depend upon the nature of the radicals attached to the hydrolysable imino group, the position of the methyl group with respect to the imino group and the molecular weight of the radicals attached to the imino group. (ii) Introduction of asymmetry increases the relative rate of hydrolysis.

The substituted amides of acetoacetic acid mentioned below have been hydrolysed with a standard solution of (i) alcoholic potassium hydroxide (ii) aqueous hydrochloric acid, in order to study the rate of hydrolysis in alkaline and acid media.

*1. Acetoacetanilide. *2. Acetoacet-*o*-tolylamide. *3. Acetoacet-*p*-tolylamide.
Acetoacet-1:3:4-xylylamide. 5. Acetoacet- α -naphthylamide. 6. Acetoacet- β -naphthylamide.

The substances marked (*) had been studied by Mme. Ramart, Naik and Trivedi (*Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1934, 1, 525) at a concentration other than that adopted in this work.

The aim of undertaking the work embodied in this part is:—

- (i) To correlate the phase of chemical activity of the molecules expressed by the rate of hydrolysis with their absorption spectra.
- (ii) To investigate the several factors which govern the chemical activity of these molecules as expressed by the rate of hydrolysis.

The rate of hydrolysis would depend on:—

- (a) The nature of the grouping -NHR, according as R is phenyl, tolyl, xylyl, or naphthyl group.
- (b) The position of the alkyl group or groups, in the case of tolyl and xylyl group attached to the nitrogen.
- (c) The molecular weight and the molecular volume of the groups attached to the -CO- group in the above compounds.
- (d) The position of -NH- grouping, either α or β , as in the case of naphthylamides.

The Rate of Hydrolysis in Alkaline Medium.—The general scheme according to which hydrolysis takes place can be represented as

As regards the mechanism of the hydrolysis, Rice states:—

"It may be assumed that the hydrolysis of amides follows a mechanism similar to reactions in which an ester is hydrolysed" (Rice, "Mechanism of Homogeneous Organic Reactions" p. 121).

that of (3) and tends to cut that of (1) as reaction proceeds. The curve for absorption spectra of (2) shows a similar tendency. The curve for (4) has not maintained the same position as

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

FIG. 3

FIG. 4

FIG. 5

was expected from the absorption curve. Still, however, it may be quite clear that they tend to maintain similar character and structure in all essential points. The peculiar behaviour of xylamide can be attributed to its structure.

Moreover, it is evident, from this investigation, that the *ortho*-substituted compound shows a slower rate of hydrolysis than that of the *para*-substituted compound. This fact is in excellent agreement with a general view that "*ortho*-substitution always reduces the velocity" (Reid, *Amer. Chem. J.*, 1899, 21, 284; Acree and Nirdlinger, *ibid* 1907, 38, 489.). Mme. Ramart, Naik and Trivedi while studying hydrolysis of substituted amides of malonic acid found that *ortho*-derivative has got the lowest velocity of hydrolysis. This has been further substantiated

by the other workers in this laboratory (Naik, Trivedi, and Mehta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 15, 426; Parikh, thesis for M.Sc., Bombay University).

In Fig. 2 the velocities of hydrolysis of (1) acetoacet- α -naphthylamide and (2) acetoacet- β -naphthylamide are shown graphically. It will be seen that the greater absorption in the ultra-violet, exhibited by α -naphthylamide is translated by the greater activity, as expressed by velocity of hydrolysis of the same. Here, again the slight enhancement in the velocity of hydrolysis, when compared with the acetoacet-xylylamide, could be ascribed to the increased weight of grouping attached to the hydrolysable imino group.

In support of the above suggestion it may be urged that the molecular weights as well as the molecular volumes play an important part in determining the velocity of reaction as evidenced by the work of Kellas (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1897, 24, 221) in connection with the velocity of esterification. This fact has been substantiated by the results of other investigators.

Velocity of Hydrolysis in Acid Medium.—As regards the mechanism of the acid hydrolysis, different views are being held, though according to Rice (*loc. cit.*) the mechanism is similar to that which takes place in alkaline hydrolysis.

As stated before, in each experiment a weighed quantity of 0.01 g.-mol. of the substance was dissolved in 100 c.c. of alcohol so as to make the ultimate concentration of the solution 0.1 g.-mol. per litre. 5 C.c. of this solution and 5 c.c. of 2.5 *N*-hydrochloric acid solution were introduced in each of the eight dry, clean, wide mouthed glass-stoppered bottles and these were at once placed in an electrically regulated thermostat, maintained at 35° at a known time. At each interval of 5, 10, 20, 30 and 120 minutes, one bottle was removed from the thermostat, and ice-cold water (50 c.c.) was immediately added to arrest the reaction. 5 C.c. of 0.1 *N*-sodium nitrite solution were then added and the bottle was kept in an ice-bath for 15 minutes so as to complete the diazotisation of the amine liberated during the course of hydrolysis. The excess of sodium nitrite was subsequently titrated with 0.05 *N*-sulphanilic acid solution, using starch-iodide paper. The end-point was marked when a drop of the titrated mixture failed to give the slightest blue colour. This method was adopted in accordance with the method suggested for the quantitative determination of an amine by Phillips and Lowry (*Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1937, 20, 381). In order to eliminate the discrepancy that may arise due to a loss of the nitrous acid by volatilisation, a blank experiment was carried out in each case, 5 c.c. of the solution of the substance being replaced by 5 c.c. of alcohol, but all along adhering to the identical procedure as described above.

The results of the study of the hydrolysis have been represented graphically in Fig. 3 and the summary of the results has been given in Table II.

TABLE II

Time in minutes.	Percentage hydrolysed of						
	Acetoacet-anilide.	Acetoacet- <i>o</i> -tolylamide.	Acetoacet- <i>p</i> -tolylamide.	Acetoacet-1:3 4-xylylamide.	Acetoacet- α -naphthylamide.	Acetoacet- β -naphthylamide.	Acetanilide.
5	20'25	15'00	17'50	10'00	12'50	9'50	16'00
10	26'75	22'30	27'00	18'25	21'30	16'25	27'00
20	31'50	29'50	32'00	24'50	30'50	19'50	39'00
30	38'50	32'50	37'20	29'00	36'75	22'25	47'00
50	41'00	36'80	42'00	33'25	40'25	26'50	68'50
120	44'25	39'75	44'00	36'75	44'25	29'00	85'00

In Fig. 3 are given the curves showing the velocity of hydrolysis of (1) acetoacetanilide, (2) acetoacet-*o*-tolylamide, (3) acetoacet-*p*-tolylamide and (4) acetoacet-1:3:4-xylylamide.

It is clear from these curves that the velocity curves resemble the absorption ones in their general direction and disposition. Still, however, the similarity between these velocity curves and absorption curves, in this case, is not so much so close as it is observed in that of the results of alkaline hydrolysis. It can be assumed that the internal conditions of the molecules as regards the structure during alkaline hydrolysis remains the same as when they are studied for the ultraviolet absorption.

It is very interesting to note that the group-effect on the rate of hydrolysis is brought out here more conspicuously, because H-ion (catalyst) concentration remains the same. Any peculiar behaviour exhibited by the substances can be ascribed to the presence and arrangement of groups in the molecules.

It is observed from the curves (2) and (3) that the proximity of the methyl group brings a remarkable diminution in the rate of hydrolysis in the *ortho*-compound. This point has already been noted during the study of alkaline hydrolysis. Reid (*loc. cit.*) during his studies on hydrolysis of acid amides, observed that substitution in the ring diminishes the rate of hydrolysis by hydrogen ions, *ortho*-substitution having the greatest effect.

On comparing the curves (2) and (4) it appears that the effect of the methyl group in *ortho* position, present in acetoacet-1:3:4-xylylamide, becomes predominantly marked.

In Fig. 4 are shown the curves for the hydrolysis of (1) acetoacet- α -naphthylamide and (2) acetoacet- β -naphthylamide. On comparing these curves with those obtained in the case of alkaline hydrolysis, similar observations can be made.

In Fig. 5 are plotted the curves for the acid hydrolysis of (1) acetoacetanilide and (2) acetanilide. From a study of these it is apparent that the introduction of CH_2CO group in place of one of the hydrogens of the methyl group, situated in the side-chain of the molecule of acetanilide, considerably lowers the rate of hydrolysis.

If the structures of these substances are represented as below, it would be clearly observed that in case of acetanilide, the heavy residue, $-\text{CONHC}_6\text{H}_5$, is hanging on one of the valency bonds of carbon, the remaining three being utilised by single hydrogen atoms and so it is not balanced by any other group such as $\text{CH}_2\text{CO}-$ in acetoacetanilide.

(Acetanilide)

(Acetoacetanilide)

Eventually it may be expected that unequal distribution of valency pulls, which is highly increased in the case of acetanilide, is very likely responsible for the high chemical activity (*loc. cit.*).

Again, if we study the results of velocity of saponification of the substituted amides of cyanoacetic acid such as $\text{CH}_2(\text{CN})\text{CONHR}$, we notice that the unsymmetry in the molecule round the methylene group is responsible for the enhanced velocity of saponification of the groups $-\text{CONHR}-$ (where R may be phenyl, tolyl, xylyl or naphthyl). However, if in the molecule there is a symmetry around the methylene group, the velocity of saponification is considerably lowered down, as exhibited by the study of the substituted amides of malonic acid, *viz.*, $\text{CH}_2(\text{CONHR})_2$ (Mme. Ramart, Naik and Trivedi, *loc. cit.*).

In a series such as,

(I)

(II)

(III)

(IV)

the velocity of saponification is highest in case of (I) and lowest in the case of (IV) as can be seen from the following :—

Time.	Name.	% Hydrolysed.
3 hrs.	Acetanilide	85%
" "	Acetoacetanilide	26.16%
" "	Cyanoacetanilide	24.00%
" "	Malon-dianilide	18.00%

Two facts emerge out clearly from these observations.

1. Velocity of hydrolysis depends upon symmetry in the molecule.
2. The nature of groups such as H, -CN, -COCH₃, or -CONHR carried by the valency bond of carbon marked 3 plays an important part in deciding the speed of hydrolysis of the -CO'NHR attached to the bond marked 4.

From the above investigation, the following observations may be recorded.

1. The velocity of hydrolysis, (especially in alkaline medium) of the several compounds investigated, is in full accord with their absorption spectra.
2. The velocity of hydrolysis (alkaline or acid) appears to depend upon the nature of the radicals attached to the hydrolysable imino (-NH-) grouping.
3. The velocity of hydrolysis seems also to depend upon the position of the methyl group with regard to the imino group.

4. By introducing unsymmetry in a system like $\begin{array}{c} \text{X} \\ \diagdown \\ \text{C} \\ \diagup \\ \text{X} \end{array} \begin{array}{c} \text{Y} \\ \diagup \\ \text{C} \\ \diagdown \\ \text{Y} \end{array}$ the relative rate of hydrolysis increases.

5. The molecular weight of the radicals attached to the imino group has also some influence on the rate of hydrolysis.

These are in excellent agreement with the observations recorded by previous workers.

The authors are grateful to H. H. The Maharaja Gaekwad's Government for necessary facilities given for carrying out the above work.